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Zone Wise City Bus Services In Solapur City A Geographical Analysis

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Abstract

The present paper is deals with the city bus services in Solapur city. Solapur city has a long historical background about city bus services. It also one of the major cause of cities expansion, especially along the Akkalkot Road. A city bus service is helpful for the movement of peoples. The city goes through rapid population growth which requires very high city bus services. City bus is cheap public transport system. It reduces the traffic congestion. It also reduces the consumption of fuel. Environmentally city bus is pollution controller with substitute large number of vehicles. The characteristic features of a Solapur city are the result of the combination of various factors like topography, climate, history, economy and culture etc. since these characteristics vary, and very town/city is unique and has a certain distinctive characteristics. These urban characteristics are however never static. They change both over time and space.

With the development of the economy other factors, like population growth, urbanization and improved technology have a combined effect Solapur city, which grow bigger and more complex. The present research focuses on the city bus services with reference to administrative zones. Solapur city has total eight administrative zones. The zone wise analysis of city bus services is discussed in this paper.

Key Words: City Bus Service, Buffer Analysis, Multiple Ring Analysis, Transportation, SMT, Operating Site

Introduction

Transportation plays an important role in economic growth and development. The introduction of railway has been historically the most powerful single factor in the process of economic development of industrilsed nations of the world. Transportation essential for economic development because the total cost of production and distribution without adequate facilities are moving goods and people from one place to another Economic and Social activities can be carried an only in a limited way.

Geographical conditions like topography and climate restrict the use of certain type of means of transport and thus limit the efficiency of transport. Transport developments are closely connected with scientific and technological progress.

Objectives: -

The present study has certain specific objectives.

1. To study history of city bus services in study area.
2. To study distribution pattern of city bus services in Solapur city.
3. To study zone wise distribution of city bus services and need for future availability in study area.

Study Area

The city of Solapur is located in between 17⁰43' 30" North latitudes and 17⁰46' 15" North latitudes to 75⁰52' 10" East to 75⁰58' 20" East longitude. The city lies about 550 meters above the mean sea level. The area under the jurisdiction of the Solapur, in Municipal Corporation has an area of 178.5 square kilometer. (Fig 1.1) The city is bounded by 16 villages. According to 2007 and 2011 the Population of city was estimated 977162 and 1133009 respectively. After the 1992 extension number of villages included in Solapur city.

Fig 1.1

Data Collection and Methodology

The present study covering an entire city as the study area. The analysis is purely based on quantitative data collected from Solapur Municipal Transport Department. The secondary data collected from census of India, published by the directorate of economics and statistics, Government of Maharashtra, District census handbook, Gazetteers. The annual reports of SMT are refereed. The collected data is shown by cartographic and Buffer analysis Methods.

City Bus as a Means of Transportation

Millions of people rely on buses for daily transport and longer trips. The term bus is short for the French word 'Omnibus' which refers to a slow local train. Municipal buses are usually operated by local and state transit agencies and are supported by passenger's fares and public funds. While buses range widely in size and form, depending on their function, the standard bus ranges in length from 10.7 m to 12.2 m and can carry more than 50 passengers. Some buses are articulated, trailing an additional unit via flexible joints. Double-decker buses have a second and sometimes third, riding level. Riders pay a fare with cash or tokens on the bus. Passengers also purchase passes, prior to entering the bus, for a specific period of time. Buses are still however, the most used form of mass transit in the city. Government often promotes the use of buses because they are comparatively environmentally sound, inexpensive and safe and they help cut down on traffic congestion.

Solapur Municipal Transports

The Solapur Municipal Transport completed 50 years of its service. The service was started after independence on 10th January 1949. Members of the Solapur Municipal Council made a proposal on 8th March 1945; however British government approved the proposal after frequent requests and appeals in the year 1949. Initially two special buses were started from Panchkatta to Mariaai Chowk and kumbhar Ves to Mariaai Chowk during morning hours especially for Mill workers. The Solapur Municipal Council started city bus service as back as in 1949. Before that the private company used to provide city bus service. Till the establishment of Solapur Municipal Corporation i.e. up to 1964 the city bus service was administered by then Municipal Council. After 1st April 1965 the bus service came under the control of the transport committee of the Municipal Corporation. The Municipal Corporation provided a separate site for the purpose of maintenance and causal repairs etc. which is known as central workshop site. Recently Municipal Transport Authority has started to operate the city buses from the site of Rajendra Chowk shopping centre near the Jodbasawanna Chowk.

Solapur Municipal Transport is the public transport service provider for the city of Solapur and surrounding region. It includes rural areas also. Initially Solapur Municipal Transport had 12 buses, 5 Routes, travelled 14 miles per day giving annual income of 75438. The minimum cost of ticket was 1 aana and maximum of 4 aane. At present SMT have **93 Buses** on the roads on a given day. The total routes have almost reached **56**, covers 18500 km. per day. The city bus transports the 70000 passengers daily. It gives monthly income of 1 crore. The bus fares are charged on the basis of distance travelled. The fare charges range from minimum of Rs. 5 for 2 Km to Rs. 25 for journey of 40 km. The funds have been issued under the scheme Jawaharlal Nehru National Urban Renewal Mission for purchase 190 new buses, Out of 145 are big buses, 35 Mini buses and 10 Volvo buses. Recently 10 New Volvo Buses are included in the SMT services which used for longer routes only.

Solapur Municipal Transport Utility Services

Solapur Municipal Transport authority has various operating sites in various administrative zones. Currently these operating sites have working buses. Table 1.1 and figure 1.3 shows the distribution of buses. For the study of utility services the zone III shows highest concentration of buses. This zone have four operating site. These are Kumbhar Ves, Rajendra

Chowk, Kontam Chowk and Kanna Chowk. It is one of the most accessible zone in the study area. The zone I and VII shows Medium concentration of buses. In the zone I Panjrappaul Chowk is the only operating site. The zone VII have two operating site, one is located in the Railway station and second is at Dak Bangala. The very low concentration of buses in the zone V and zone II,IV,VI and VIII shows absence of operating site as well as distribution of buses. The very high accessibility is found in zone I, III and VII and very low accessibility is found in zone II, IV, VI, and VIII.

Fig 1.2

Table 1.1 SMT Zone Wise Distributions of Buses with Special Reference to Operating Site

Zones	SMT Operating Site	Buses	Total
Zone I	Panjrappaul Chowk	28	28
Zone II	Nil	00	00
Zone III	Rajendra Chowk	14	41
	Kontam Chowk	24	
	Kanna Chowk	02	
	Kumbar Ves	01	
Zone IV	Nil	00	00
Zone V	Saiful	1	02
	Aasara	1	
Zone VI	Nil	00	00
Zone VII	Railway Station	21	22
	Dak Bangla	01	
Zone VIII	Nil	00	00
			93

(Source: Solapur Municipal Transport Head office, Solapur)

Fig 1.3

Buffer Analysis

The buffer zone around a map feature measured in the units of distance and time. A buffer analysis technique is very useful to show the proximity analysis.

Point Buffer Analysis

Figure 1.4, 1.5 and 1.6 shows 1km, 2km and 3km buffer along the each operating site. These buffer rings cover an area up to 3 km from the operating site. These areas come under public utility services. The use of city bus transport gives benefits for the people in this area. It will show the most accessible zone of the city in each zone and it represents the high traffic flow pattern.

Multiple Ring Buffer Analysis

Figure 1.7 shows Multiple Ring Buffer analysis along the operating site in the study area. The brown Colour shows the 1km buffer, blue colour shows the 2km buffer and pink colour shows 3km buffer along the operating site. This buffer covers the area of 3km.

Fig 1.4

Fig 1.5

Fig 1.6

Fig 1.7

Conclusions

City bus service is a cheap public transport system. City bus services cover the most of the area. The SMT is now increasing their buses to provide services to all the areas with high frequency.

1. The highest concentration of city bus services in the zone III.
2. The Medium Concentration of city services in the zone I and VII.

3. The lowest concentration of city bus services in the zone V.
4. The zones II, IV, VI and VIII show absence of city bus operating sites but area serve b remaining zones.
5. The zone III is most accessible zone in Solapur city. It's having four operating sites.
6. The buffer ring analysis shows the centre of the city is most accessible.

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Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts of interest.

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